

USE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY COMMUNICATIONS IN ENGLISH LEARNING

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Annotation: *The article argues that in the context of interdisciplinary communication, students need to look for the most convenient ways to achieve the best results in learning English.*

Key words: *language, motivation, didactic principle, conceptual connections, student.*

At the current stage of development of the theory and practice of teaching, the issue of creating motivations for the educational activities of vocational school students is rightly one of the central issues. The quality of teaching depends in many ways on how well it is motivated in the eyes of the students. The problem of motivation is especially important when there is no natural need for communication. Therefore, for a foreign language teacher, the interest of vocational school students is important not only in the results of their work, but also in the process of achieving this result. One of the resources to increase the motivation of vocational school students to learn is to use these interdisciplinary connections wisely. Interdisciplinary interdependence is the interconnectedness of curricula due to the system of disciplines and didactic objectives. The didactic principles of the scientific nature and systematization of knowledge require the regulation of individual disciplines in the curriculum in such a way that the study of one subject can be based on the knowledge imparted in other disciplines. Interdisciplinary communication is an appropriate tool for a comprehensive approach to student education. The presence of interdisciplinary links in the curriculum allows high school students to form an understanding of the system of concepts and universal laws, and among high school students general theories and complex problems. Interdisciplinary connections increase the level of science teaching and its role in shaping the student's scientific outlook. There are different types of interdisciplinary relationships:

- 1) information connections - data-level connections between academic disciplines;
- 2) conceptual connections aimed at the formation of general concepts for related entities;
- 3) theoretical connections - systems of scientific knowledge in a particular field of science;

4) philosophical connections reflecting the categories of materialist dialectics. “Interdisciplinary connections play an important role in the teaching of any subject. They primarily serve as a basis for the full understanding and comprehension of new knowledge, the formation and development of skills; second, they allow the generalization and systematization of existing linguistic and speech experience and ensure the completeness of knowledge” (VA Onishuk). The materials studied on this subject suggested ways to make interdisciplinary connections in English language teaching, but nowhere does it say that English material is given one or two years or more before the deadline and therefore only the teacher faces difficulties (i.e., because he must first be able to correctly explain the material in his native language, and this takes time, moreover, it is not welcomed and probably only in some cases), but also causes difficulties in children. Every student should learn a foreign language based on their knowledge of their mother tongue.

It should be noted that there are disciplines of the vocational school cycle that need to be relied upon when teaching English. Concepts such as synonyms, antonyms, dialogue, monologue, description, narration, reasoning, compositional structure of speech, etc.; from the literature - quoting text, thought, main idea, poems, proverbs, sayings and so on. From fine arts - portrait painting, landscape, subject composition is the basis for the teacher. It is necessary to create prospects for the use of interdisciplinary communication in teaching English. The first direction is related to the expansion of a meaningful reading plan in English by enriching it with linguistic (and in specialized classes - non-linguistic) information from different disciplines. The second area, which characterizes the professional aspect of this subject, includes improving general education skills, which increases the effectiveness of foreign language teaching, updating students' knowledge acquired in the learning process, and will be focused on systematization. They will also be used in the foreign language and other disciplines. Let us first consider this problem in relation to the content of our subject matter. From the point of view of enriching students' speech with (additional) linguistic information, two perspectives on the use of a foreign language in teaching a foreign language are important: increasing the overall share of universal information and It is necessary to increase the regional aspect of the unit, to increase the informational aspect of foreign language teaching in vocational schools. Considering the following points in the humanities, their necessity seems to be:

- first, the materials of regional studies, mainly as a means of communication in a foreign language, reflect the peculiarities of the foreign language;
- secondly, when reading material about the country of the language being studied in English, students significantly increase their chances of getting acquainted with the

reality of the country of the language being studied, they have almost no opportunity to get acquainted with them when studying other subjects.

In the modern era of broad international cooperation and dialogue of cultures, attention should be paid to reconsidering the attitude to the country of language, in particular, to avoid ideological labels, in which, first of all, to see the image of friendship, loyalty to universal values. The idea of combining knowledge from different disciplines is, as a rule, most effectively implemented in texts that contain information (or events, their assessments) from the disciplines of history and literature.

As for general learning skills, priority should be given to those who seek to learn from the text and describe reading as an informative process. It is intended to divide the text into semantic parts and to distinguish basic information from them, to form the ability to distinguish between basic and detailed information. This and other skills are specific to the national and cultural concepts inherent in the English language develops the ability to understand regional geographical interpretation based on the formation of interdisciplinary specific skills. The ability to establish a causal link between history, geography, and literature in reading English texts forms the ability to apply the knowledge gained in the classroom to other disciplines. In connection with the development of general education and special interdisciplinary skills, it is expedient to identify methods of their formation, which include activation, comparison and systematization. Mastering these techniques allows students to establish and apply the English language to other disciplines [6, 45]. The rules set out to prove the importance and obligation of relying on other disciplines in the process of learning English can be considered very convincing. Mastering foreign language activities based on interdisciplinary connections (where the points of contact between vocational school subjects are clearly defined and ways to create motivation) meet the different interests of students, allowing them to take into account their individual characteristics and tendencies It is natural to create the most convenient opportunities for the practical use of language as a means of communication. As a result of observing the practical lessons in the classroom, conversations with teachers, the use of interdisciplinary communication is a random, episodic work moments, we are convinced that they are unique methodological findings of a small number of teachers. This situation is unsatisfactory, as the existing literature emphasizes the importance of taking into account interdisciplinary information, defines the educational functions of interdisciplinary communication and, most importantly, suggests a number of teaching methods for their use: interdisciplinary content issues , interdisciplinary problem questions, complex assignments, interdisciplinary tasks, complex visual aids, interdisciplinary texts, interdisciplinary crossword puzzles, interdisciplinary tests, interdisciplinary homework, etc.

Thus, influencing the selection and structure of teaching materials in a number of interdisciplinary disciplines, increasing the consistency of students' knowledge, activating teaching methods, focusing on the use of complex forms of organization of education, ensuring unity. In one way or another, the implementation of interdisciplinary links in the system helps to shape the need for vocational school students not to limit themselves to a single topic in explaining certain events.

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